

Health Through Environmental Protection

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Abstract

Environmental protection promotes health. This article discusses the environment's impact and preservation on health, its role in public health, and what the future may hold for environmental health and safety activities. A diverse range of public activities, including these activities.

What Exactly is Environment?

En = In, Viron = Circle is an old French word.

The environment encompasses all of the natural conditions in which animals live. Climate, geography, physiography, and faunal conditions are all examples of external conditions.

What is Health?

It is a stable state of physical, mental, and social well-being, not simply the absence of illness.

What is Environmental Protection?

Environmental protection is the practice of individuals, organizations, and governments protecting the natural environment.

Objectives of the Environmental Protection

- The preservation and safeguards of human and animal health, integrity, biodiversity, and ecosystem health, genetic resources, animal and plant species, soil nutrient, natural sites and geographic resources, cultural heritage, and anthropogenic resources.
- Creating conditions for the constrained, rational, and sustainable management of both living and non-living nature, the preservation of ecological stability of nature, the quantity and quality of natural resources, and the prevention of environmental dangers and threats.
- Raising awareness of the importance of environmental protection and preservation as well as

integrating environmental education courses into school curricula.

- Protecting vulnerable areas and reclaiming particularly deteriorated areas in order to improve their quality.

WHO recommends unhealthy environments are responsible for an estimated 12.6 million deaths each year, accounting for nearly one-quarter of all global deaths. More than 100 diseases and injuries are caused by environmental risk factors such as air, water, and soil pollution, chemical exposure, climate change, and ultraviolet radiation.

All organisms rely on their surroundings for the energy and materials they require to live: clean air, potable water, nutritious food, and safe places to live. For the majority of human history, increases in longevity were due to better access to these necessities. Agriculture, sanitation, water treatment, and hygiene advancements have had far greater effects on human health than medical science.

Environmental factors were responsible for an estimated 24% of the global burden of disease (healthy life years lost) and an estimated 23% of all deaths (premature mortality) worldwide. The proportion of deaths attributed to the environment among children aged 0-14 years was as high as 36%. Due to differences in environmental exposure and access to health care across the regions, there were significant regional differences in the environmental contribution to various disease conditions. For example, while environmental causes were responsible for 25% of all deaths in developing regions, they were responsible for only 17% of deaths in developed regions. Furthermore, the causal pathway between environmental hazard and disease outcome is often complex.

Inadequate pedestrian and cycling infrastructure, for example, contributes significantly to injuries from road traffic accidents (40%). However, the long-term health effects of certain changes in urban geography and mobility patterns have yet to be quantified. Environmental risk factors such as occupational exposure to dust and chemicals, as well as indoor air pollution from household solid fuel use, are thought to be responsible for 42% of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), a progressive loss of lung function. Other sources of indoor and outdoor air pollution, such as transportation and second-hand tobacco smoke, also play a role.

What can we and the public do about environmental risks to health?

Many of the problems at the crossroads of health and the environment revolve around balancing risks and benefits. Pesticides, for example, play a crucial role in rising crop yields, but they can also be harmful to human health and the environment. Alternatives to pesticide use result in health trade-offs.

Environmental pollution can be avoided, which can save lives. There is abundant scientific evidence demonstrating how environmental, chemical, and air pollution, as well as climate change, endanger and

harm our health. India has a real opportunity to protect and improve the health of its people, as well as to prevent major chronic health epidemics.

Many goals have an environmental health component; key elements are highlighted below.

GOAL 1- Eradicate extreme poverty and hunger:

Because many environmentally influenced diseases result in lost profits, reducing exposure to environmental risk factors indirectly contributes to poverty reduction. In addition, the disability or death of one fruitful household member can have a ripple effect on the entire household. **GOAL 2 - Raise awareness among the people towards the environment**

More people should try to be willing to take part in greenery, to buy organic, and, ultimately, to protect the environment.

Goal 3 - Protection of the most vulnerable

A polluted environment is especially hazardous to children, the elderly, the sick, and the poor.

GOAL- 4 Reduce child mortality:

The fatality rate from environmentally-mediated disease conditions in children under the age of five is 180 times higher in the poorest performing region than in the best performing region. In terms of just diarrhea and lower respiratory infections, two of the most serious childhood killers, environmental initiatives could save the lives of over 2 million children under the age of five each year, contributing to the achievement of a key goal.

GOAL- 5- Improve maternal health

Environmental interventions can help by providing a safe home environment, which is critical for the health of children and pregnant women. A contaminated home environment, on the other hand, poses a risk to the mother and her infant baby. Childbirth, for example, necessitates safe drinking water and sanitation facilities.

GOAL- 6 Combat HIV AIDS, MALARIA and other diseases:

According to the findings of this study, over 500,000 people die each year from malaria, and over a quarter of a million die from HIV/AIDS as a result of environmental and occupational causes. A significant portion of malaria may be attributable to easily modifiable environmental factors such as land use, irrigation, and agricultural practices.

GOAL 7 – Population control to save the earth:

Overpopulation occurs when the sheer number of people exceeds the capacity of the environment. Environmental degradation, reduced quality of life, and a population crash are all possible outcomes.

